

Mixed-ligand complex formation equilibria of Cu^{II} with glycyglycinate and guanylurea

Tannistha Roy Barman and G. N. Mukherjee*

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, University of Calcutta,
92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : gmchem@rediffmail.com Fax : 91-33-2351-9755/2241-3222

Manuscript received 26 March 2009, revised 1 June 2009, accepted 3 June 2009

Abstract : Combined spectrophotometric and computer based pH metric investigation on the mixed ligand complex formation equilibria of Cu^{II} with glycyglycine (H₃N⁺CH₂CONHCH₂COO⁻, HGG[±]) and guanylurea [H₂¹NC(=O)²NHC(=NH)⁴NH₂, HGu] in aqueous solution at 25 ± 1 °C, at a fixed ionic strength, I = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (NaNO₃), indicate variety of binary and ternary complexes : [Cu(GG)⁺aq], [Cu(GG-H)(H₂O)], [Cu(GG-H)(OH)⁻], [Cu(Gu)⁺aq], [Cu(Gu)(OH)], [Cu(Gu-H)(OH)⁻], [Cu(GG-H)(Gu)⁻], [Cu(GG-H)(Gu-H)²⁻] and [Cu(GG-H)(Gu-2H)³⁻]. At pH ≤ 4.5, GG⁻ ion provides neutral (NH₂, C=O) bidentate chelation to Cu^{II} and above pH 4.5~5, coordinated GG⁻ is transformed to amide deprotonated glycyglycinate dianion, (GG-H)²⁻, which provides terdentate equatorial (NH₂, N⁻, COO⁻) chelation to Cu^{II}. Consequently in the electronic spectra λ_{max} of Cu^{II} is blue shifted. λ_{max} of the ternary complex, [Cu(GG-H)(Gu)⁻], indicates a square pyramidal geometry existing in a isomeric structural equilibrium, involving bidentate axial (=NH) and equatorial (O=C)/(H₂¹N)/(H¹N=C) chelation by Gu⁻ ion. Above pH 7, [Cu(GG-H)(Gu)⁻] undergoes deprotonation of the (H¹N) and HO-(enolic) moieties of coordinated Gu⁻ in successive steps.

Keywords : Glycyglycine, guanylurea, copper(II), mixed ligand complexes, formation constants.

Introduction

Interaction of metal ions with amino acids and small peptides in aqueous solution provides simple models for metal-protein interactions in enzymic processes. Studies on mixed-ligand complex formation equilibria of biological metal ions with amino acids and small peptides in presence of various auxiliary ligands having biochemically relevant functional groups give useful clues to enzyme-metal-substrate interactions¹.

Ambidentism in metal ion coordination with peptide (i.e. amide) bond (-CONH-) is well known². In weakly acidic solution (pH ≤ 4), the amide bond in dipeptides such as glycyglycine coordinates metal ions, such as Cu^{II}, with its carbonyl O-atom. Above pH 4.5~5, the carbonyl O-atom is replaced by the deprotonated amide N-atom, involving a structural equilibrium, with consequent blue shift of the electronic spectral absorption maximum of Cu^{II}, due to enhancement of ligand field strength, as a neutral O-donor atom is replaced by a more strongly ba-

sic anionic amide N-donor atom. Due to the planarity imposed by amide bonds, the deprotonated amide N-atoms, in metal complexes with poly peptides, tend to coordinate metal ions equatorially. Cu^{II} shows so strong affinity for equatorially coordinated deprotonated amide N-atoms as ligands, that even strongly coordinating (N,N) bidentate ligands, such as 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridine are forced to coordinate Cu^{II} from one axial and one equatorial positions in their mixed ligand complexes with Cu^{II} and poly peptide ligands³⁻⁵.

Varied modes of coordination of guanylurea [H₂¹N(C=O)²NHC(=NH)⁴NH₂, HGu], in binary Cu^{II}-HGu and ternary Cu^{II}-glycine-HGu complexes, have been revealed from our earlier investigation⁶. With a view to elucidate the modes of metal ion coordination by the simplest dipeptide ligand, glycyglycine (H₃N⁺CH₂-CONHCH₂COO⁻, HGG[±]), in presence of the strongly coordinating bidentate ligand, guanylurea, having isoelectronic and isostructural amide and amidine functions in

suitable positions within the same molecule (Scheme 1), the present paper describes the results of a combined spectrophotometric and computer based pH metric equilibrium study on the mixed ligand complex formation of Cu^{II} with glycylglycinate and guanylurea in aqueous solution, at 25 ± 1 °C at a fixed ionic strength, *I* = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (NaNO₃).

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

1 : 1 Cu^{II} : HGG[±] binary equilibria :

In dilute acidic solution (pH ~2) glycylglycine (HGG[±]) exists in its protonated form (H₂GG⁺). The added proton remains associated with -COO⁻ group. With rise of pH, the -COOH and the NH₃⁺ groups deprotonate in successive steps, in the pH ranges 2 < pH < 4.5 and 7.5 < pH < 9.5 respectively (Fig. 1), producing first the zwitterionic species, (HGG[±]) and then the anionic species, (GG⁻). The amide (-CONH-) group remains neutral

Fig. 1. Representative pH titration curves (*M* = mol dm⁻³) : 1, 0.005 (*M*) HNO₃; 2, (1) + 0.001 (*M*) H₂Gu⁺; 3, (1) + 0.001 (*M*) HGG[±]; 4, (2) + 0.001 (*M*) Cu^{II}; 5, (3) + 0.001 (*M*) Cu^{II}; 6, (5) + 0.001 (*M*) H₂Gu⁺; initial volume = 0.025 dm³, titrant = 0.1 (*M*) NaOH, ionic strength, *I* = 0.1 (*M*) NaNO₃.

in the experimental pH range in the absence of a metal ion. Complex formation of Cu^{II} with HGG[±], in 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : HGG[±] binary system, starts around pH ~3. Two moles of H⁺ per mole of Cu^{II} are released in the pH range 3–7.5, at which the free ligand exists as HGG[±]. The speciation curves (Fig. 2a), indicate simultaneous formation (Scheme 2), of two 1 : 1 complexes, [Cu(GG)⁺], (7) and [Cu(GG-H)], (8), (Table 1) where, GG⁻ and (GG-H)²⁻ represent the glycylglycinate mono anion (H₂NCH₂CONHCH₂COO⁻) and amide deprotonated glycylglycinate dianion, (H₂NCH₂CON⁻CH₂COO⁻) respectively.

GG⁻ ligand ion complex (7) provides bidentate neutral (N,O) chelation to Cu^{II} using its amino N-atom and

Fig. 2. Speciation curves of (a) 1 : 1 Cu^{II} · HGG[±] and (b) 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : HGGu systems : 1, H₂GG⁺; 2, HGG[±]; 3, H₂Gu⁺; 4, HGGu, 5, [Cu(OH)⁺], 6, [Cu(OH)₂]; 7, [Cu(GG)⁺]; 8, [Cu(GG-H)]; 9, [Cu(GG-H)(OH)⁻]; 10, [Cu(Gu)⁺]; 11, [Cu(Gu)(OH)]; FM = Free Cu^{II}, FB₁ = Free GG⁻; FB₂ = Free Gu⁻.

Table 1. Formation constants (β_{pqrs}) of binary and mixed ligand Cu^{II} complexes with glycylglycine (HGG^{\pm}) and guanylurea (HGu) in aqueous solution

Ionic strength, $I = 0.1 \text{ (M) NaNO}_3$ at $25 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

Sl. no.	Complex species	p	q	r	s	$\log \beta_{pqrs}$
1.	$[\text{H}_2\text{GG}^+]$	0	1	0	-2	11.31
2.	$[\text{HGG}^\pm]$	0	1	0	-1	8.15
3.	$[\text{H}_2\text{Gu}^+]$	0	0	1	-2	10.20
4.	$[\text{HGu}]$	0	0	1	-1	8.20
5.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+]$	1	0	0	1	-6.29
6.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2]$	1	0	0	2	-13.05
7.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{GG})^+]$	1	1	0	0	5.74
8.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{GG}-\text{H})]$	1	1	0	1	1.12
9.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{GG}-\text{H})(\text{OH})^-]$	1	1	0	2	-8.74
10.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{Gu})^+]$	1	0	1	0	5.61
11.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{Gu})(\text{OH})]$	1	0	1	1	-0.24
12.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{GG}-\text{H})(\text{Gu})^-]$	1	1	1	1	6.10
13.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{GG}-\text{H})(\text{Gu}-\text{H})^{2-}]$	1	1	1	1	-2.36
14.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{GG}-\text{H})(\text{Gu}-2\text{H})^{3-}]$	1	1	1	3	-11.26

Scheme 2

amide carbonyl O-atom, leaving the $-\text{COO}^-$ group uncoordinated due to stereochemical reason. (7) passes through a concentration maximum ($\sim 10\%$) around $\text{pH} \geq 4.5$. Both the complexes, (7) and (8) take up appropriate number of solvent H_2O molecules to satisfy square planar coordination of Cu^{II} . With rise of pH , (7) is transformed in to (8), through amide deprotonation, involving the structural equilibrium (Scheme 3), where, the amide carbonyl O-atom is replaced by the deprotonated amide N-atom and the $-\text{COO}^-$ group is also brought to a chelating position². Thus, a neutral bidentate (N,O) chelating glycylglycinate monoanion, GG^- is intra molecularly transformed into tridentate (N,N⁻,O⁻) chelating glycylglycinate dianion, $(\text{GG}-\text{H})^{2-}$, within the coordination sphere of Cu^{II} .

Due to planarity of the peptide bond^{2,3}, and preference of Cu^{2+} (d^9) to achieve a square planar geometry, all the three donor atoms of the ligand $(\text{GG}-\text{H})^{2-}$ ion in

Scheme 3

(8) tend to coordinate Cu^{II} equatorially, as supported from single crystal X-ray diffraction measurements on the mixed ligand Cu^{II} complexes, $[\text{Cu}(\text{GG}-\text{H})(\text{B})]$, where, B = heteroaromatic N-bases^{5,6}. $\text{pK}^{\text{H}}_{[\text{Cu}(\text{GG})]}$ value :

$$\text{pK}^{\text{H}}_{[\text{Cu}(\text{GG})]} = \log \beta_{1010} - \log \beta_{1011} \quad (1)$$

of ($\sim 4.62 \pm 0.05$) for such metal promoted amide deprotonation equilibrium, (7) \rightleftharpoons (8), (Scheme 3), is a measure of the enhancement of acidity of the amide proton and reflects the strong affinity of Cu^{II} for deprotonated amide N-atom over the amide carbonyl oxygen atom.

Replacement of a neutral amide carbonyl O-atom by an anionic amide N-atom and replacement of a H_2O molecule by the $-\text{COO}^-$ group, result in an enhancement of ligand field strength around Cu^{II} . Consequently, the electronic spectral absorption maximum (λ_{max}) of Cu^{II} is blue shifted from 716 nm around $\text{pH} 4$, at which the complex (7) shows a concentration maximum ($\sim 10\%$) along with $\text{Cu}^{2+}(\text{aq})$ and (8), $\sim 40\%$ each, to 635 nm around $\text{pH} 5.5$, at which the amide deprotonated complex (8) reaches its concentration maximum ($\sim 90\%$). Tentative λ_{max} values for 4-coordinated, square planar Cu^{II} complexes with glycolpeptides² may be calculated using the relation (2) :

$$\lambda_{\text{max}} (\text{nm}) = 10^3 / [0.301 (\text{C}=\text{O}/\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{OH}^-) + 0.342 (\text{COO}^-) + 0.453 (\text{NH}_2) + 0.485 (= \text{N}^-)] \quad (2)$$

where, the groups in the parentheses represent the number of such coordinating groups (total not exceeding 4) and the numerical coefficients are their ligand field contributions in μm^{-1} . Experimental λ_{max} value (635 nm) of 1 : 1 $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} : \text{HGG}^\pm$ mixture at $\text{pH} \sim 5.5$ corresponding to the concentration maximum of the amide deprotonated complex (8) is in close agreement with the calculated λ_{max} value $\sim 632.5 \text{ nm}$ for a square planar $\text{Cu}[(\text{H}_2\text{N})(\text{N}^-\text{C}=\text{O})(\text{COO}^-)(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ geometry (Scheme 3).

With rise of pH above $\text{pH} 8$, another buffer region corresponding to one mole of H^+ per mole of Cu^{II} is

appeared (Fig. 1), but no further blue shift in the λ_{\max} value is observed. This suggests deprotonation of a coordinated H₂O molecule in the [Cu(GG-H)] (aq) complex (8) to produce the ternary hydroxo complex [Cu(GG-H)(OH)] (9) in this last step. Since H₂O and OH⁻ ion provide ligand fields of comparable strength, λ_{\max} remains practically unchanged on raising the pH of the solution above pH 8. The pK^H (8) value :

$$pK^H(8) = \log \beta_{1011} - \log \beta_{1012} \quad (3)$$

of (~9.86) for deprotonation of (8) to (9) reflects the enhancement of acidity of equatorially coordinated H₂O molecule in square planar Cu^{II} complexes. Decline in the concentration of (8) above pH 8, with simultaneous building up of concentrations of (9), Cu(OH)₂ (6) and free ligand GG⁻ ion (FB₁), indicate partial decomposition of (8) according to,

along with its deprotonation to (9).

1 : 1 Cu^{II} : HG_u binary equilibria :

In dilute acidic solution (pH ~2), guanylurea exists in its protonated form (H₂Gu⁺), which provides two well separated buffer regions, pH < 4 and 7 < pH < 9 due to successive deprotonation of its ¹NH₃⁺ (or ⁴NH₃⁺) and ³NH moieties (Scheme 1), ultimately forming the monoanion, Gu⁻. Complex formation with Cu^{II} commences around pH ≥ 4, with simultaneous appearance of the species : [Cu(Gu)⁺(aq)] (10), [Cu(OH)⁺] (5) and [Cu(Gu)(OH)] (11) (Fig. 2b), indicating the existence of a composite equilibria (Scheme 4) :

Scheme 4

The complex (10) is transformed to complex (11) above pH 5.5, possibly due to deprotonation of a coordinated

H₂O molecule. Low pK^H value,

$$pK^H(10) = \log \beta_{1100} - \log \beta_{1101} \quad (5)$$

of ~5.85 for this transformation reflects the enhancement of acidity of equatorially coordinated H₂O molecule in the [Cu(Gu)⁺(aq)] complex (10)

Above pH 7.5, concentration of the ternary hydroxo complex (11) declines with simultaneous building up of concentrations of Cu(OH)₂ and the free ligand Gu⁻ ion (FB₂), suggesting decomposition of (11) according to :

Since the modes of metal ion coordination of the iso-electronic and iso-structural amide [-C(=O)NH₂] and the amidine [-C(=NH)NH₂] moieties in guanylurea are similar to those of the amide [-C(=O)NH-] bond in peptides, tentative λ_{\max} values of Cu^{II}-guanylurea complexes may be calculated using the same form of the eq. (2) described before. Interestingly, Cu^{II}-guanylurea complexes also show blue shift of the λ_{\max} with rise of pH, similar to the Cu^{II}-glycyglycinate complexes.

Guanylurea anion, Gu⁻, in the (1 : 1) Cu^{II}-Gu complex (10) may provide bidentate chelation to Cu^{II} in three different modes : (C=O, =³N⁻) (10a), (= ¹NH, =³N⁻) (10b) and (H₂¹N, =³N⁻) (10c). Two molecules of H₂O from solvent water may coordinate Cu^{II} in this complex, giving Cu^{II} a square planar geometry in these structures (Scheme 5). Calculated λ_{\max} values for the structures (10a), (10b) and (10c) are 722, 722 and 650 nm respectively. The experimental λ_{\max} value (745 nm) of 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : HG_u mixture at pH ~5.5, at which the complex (10) passes through a concentration maximum, is in close agreement with the calculated λ_{\max} values for the structures (10a) and (10b). Experimental λ_{\max} (637 nm) at pH ≥ 7.5, at which the ternary hydroxo complex [Cu(Gu)(OH)] (11) almost reaches a plateau (~85%), is in close agreement with the calculated λ_{\max} corresponding to structure (11). These observations suggest that at pH ≤ 6, the complex [Cu(Gu)(H₂O)₂⁺] (10) may exist in isomeric structures (10a) and or (10b). With rise of pH, it isomerizes to structure (10c), through which it deprotonates to (11) (Scheme 5).

1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : HGG[±] : HG_u ternary equilibria :

Complex formation in the 1 : 1 : 1 ternary Cu^{II} : HGG[±] : HG_u system starts above pH 4.5. Minor amounts

(~ 10%) of each of the binary complexes, $[\text{Cu}(\text{GG})_{(\text{aq})}^+]$ (7) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{Gu})_{(\text{aq})}^+]$ (10) persist in the pH range 5–7. The ternary hydroxo complex, $[\text{Cu}(\text{Gu})(\text{OH})]$ (11) appears above pH 6 and passes through a concentration maximum ($\leq 8\%$) around pH 7–7.5. The major Cu^{II} containing species in the pH range 5–8, however, is the amide deprotonated binary complex, $[\text{Cu}(\text{GG}-\text{H})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ (8), which passes through a concentration maximum (~ 55%) at pH ~ 7. As the speciation curves (Fig. 3) imply, the complex (8) may be formed through direct reaction of $\text{Cu}^{2+}(\text{aq})$ ion with HGG^\pm and also through intermediate formation of complex (7), (Schemes 2 and 6). The ternary complex, $[\text{Cu}(\text{GG}-\text{H})(\text{Gu})^-]$ (12), appears around pH ~ 6 and passes through a concentration maximum (~ 65%) at pH ~ 8.5. Since the height of the concentration maximum of (12) is greater than that of (8), so the complex (12) is formed not only through the reaction of (8) with HGu , but also through direct reaction of $\text{Cu}^{2+}(\text{aq})$ with HGG^\pm and HGu and as well as from the reaction of (11) with HGG^\pm (Schemes 5 and 6).

The ternary complex (12) disappears above pH 8.5, providing another buffer region, (pH 8.5–10.5), corresponding to two moles of H^+ per mole of Cu^{II} , with simultaneous building up of concentrations of the complexes,

Fig. 3. Speciation curves of 1 : 1 : 1 $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} : \text{HGu} : \text{HGG}^\pm$ system: 1, $[\text{H}_2\text{GG}^+]$; 2, $[\text{HGG}^\pm]$; 3, $[\text{H}_2\text{Gu}^+]$; 4, HGu ; 5, $[\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+]$; 6, $[\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2]$; 7, $[\text{Cu}(\text{GG})^+]$; 8, $[\text{Cu}(\text{GG}-\text{H})]$; 9, $[\text{Cu}(\text{GG}-\text{H})(\text{OH})^-]$; 10, $[\text{Cu}(\text{Gu})^+]$; 11, $[\text{Cu}(\text{Gu})(\text{OH})]$; 12, $[\text{Cu}(\text{GG}-\text{H})(\text{Gu})^-]$; 13, $[\text{Cu}(\text{GG}-\text{H})(\text{Gu}-\text{H})^{2-}]$; 14, $[\text{Cu}(\text{GG}-\text{H})(\text{Gu}-2\text{H})^{3-}]$; FM = Free Cu^{II} , FB₁ = Free GG^- ; FB₂ = Free Gu^- .

Scheme 6

$[\text{Cu}(\text{GG}-\text{H})(\text{Gu}-\text{H})^{2-}]$ (13) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{GG}-\text{H})(\text{Gu}-2\text{H})^{3-}]$ (14), resulting from stepwise deprotonation of (12). The complex (13) passes through a concentration maximum of ~ 40% around pH ~ 9.5, whereas, the complex (14) reaches a plateau of $\geq 95\%$ above pH ~ 11, indicating simultaneous two one-steps and one two-step deprotonation of (12), to produce the complexes (13) and (14) (Scheme 7).

Scheme 7

Modes of coordination of guanylurea species in 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : HGG[±] : HGu mixed ligand complexes, (12-14), may be tentatively assigned from the changes in electronic spectral λ_{max} of Cu^{II} with rise of pH of the solution, as the amide deprotonated binary complex (8) is transformed into the ternary complex (12), which successively deprotonates to (13) and (14). λ_{max} of the 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : HGG[±] : HGu mixture is blue shifted from 745 nm at pH ~4 to 636 nm at pH ~5.5-6, at which the amide deprotonated binary complex (8) passes through a concentration maximum (~55%). Sky blue colour of the solution changes to intense blue, as the (NH₂, C=O) bidentate monoanionic GG⁻ ligand ion is transformed to (NH₂, N⁻, COO⁻) tridentate (GG-H)²⁻ dianion (Scheme 3). λ_{max} value of the solution remains practically unchanged around 635-636 nm but absorbance increases in the pH range 7-9, at which the ternary complex (12) is formed in increasing amounts. This indicates that, coordination of Gu⁻ ligand ion to [Cu(GG-H)(H₂O)] (8) does not remarkably alter the ligand field strength around Cu^{II}. That is, Gu⁻ exerts ligand field of comparable strength as the coordinated H₂O molecule in the complex (8). Since the (GG-H)²⁻ ion coordinates three of the four equatorial positions around the square planar Cu^{II} (*d⁹*) ion, the bidentate chelating Gu⁻ ligand ion has to coordinate Cu^{II} from the remaining 4th equatorial position and from an axial position, in either of the following modes :

(i) (=³N⁻) equatorial and (O=C)/(NH₂)/(H¹N=C) axial, or,

(ii) (O=C)/(H₂¹N)/(H¹N=) equatorial and (=³N⁻) axial,

producing 5-coordinated square pyramidal geometry around Cu^{II}. Estimated (eq. (2)) λ_{max} values (~565-566 nm) of Cu^{II}, for structures of the types (i) with =³N⁻ as the 4th equatorial ligand are much lower than the experimental λ_{max} value (636 nm) of 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : HGG[±] : HGu mixture at pH ~7. Therefore, the first modes (i) of coordination of Gu⁻ are unlikely for the ternary complex (12). Of the three second modes (ii), the one (12a) with the (H₂¹N⁻) group as the 4th equatorial ligand is also unlikely, as the estimated value (577 nm) is much lower than the experimental λ_{max} value (636 nm) at this pH. On the other hand, the estimated λ_{max} value (~632 nm) for the remaining two structures of the modes (ii), with (O=C) or (H¹N=) as 4th equatorial ligand, (12b) and (12c) respectively (Scheme 8), are in close agreement to the experimental λ_{max} (636 nm) of 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : HGG[±] : HGu mixture at pH ~7. So these two structures (12b) and (12c) appear to be more likely for the ternary complex (12). Ligand field contributions of the isoelectronic (C=O) and (C=NH) moieties are considered to be same as that of the H₂O ligand⁷.

Although the complex (12) may exist in an equilibrium between the two isomeric structures (12b) and (12c),

Scheme 8

the latter structure (12c), with (H¹N=) as the 4th equatorial ligand, appears to be more consistent with the two step deprotonation of this ternary complex (Scheme 7). Instead of expected another blue shift of λ_{max} on further rise of pH above 10, as the ternary complex (12) undergoes deprotonation of the coordinated (H¹N=) and the free enolic-OH groups in successive steps to produce the complexes (13) and (14), a small red shift to ~645 nm is observed, which may be attributed to apical (=³N⁻) coordination⁸.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Glycylglycine (AR), obtained from Aldrich, was recrystallised from water and air dried. Guanylurea sulphate dihydrate, (GuH₂⁺)₂(SO₄²⁻).2H₂O, was prepared and purified following the literature procedure⁹. Purities of both the ligands were checked from elemental analysis and equivalent weight determination. All the other reagents were of AR grade and their solutions were prepared in double distilled CO₂ free water. Procedure for preparation and standardization of the reagent solutions, procedures of pH metric and spectrophotometric measurements and evaluation of the formation constants by computer based methods were similar to those described earlier^{6,10}. Equilibrium study for the determination of proton-ligand and metal-ligand complex formation constants involved pH-metric titrations (Fig. 1) of a series of solutions, each of initial volume 0.025 dm³, containing known amounts (0.001–0.002 mol dm⁻³) of the ligands, glycylglycine (HGG[±]) and guanylurea (HGu) in their protonated forms (H₂GG⁺ and H₂Gu⁺ respectively), in the absence and in the presence of known amounts (0.0002–0.001 mol dm⁻³) of Cu^{II} nitrate and known amount (0.005 mol dm⁻³) of free HNO₃ with a carbonate free standard 0.1 mol dm⁻³ NaOH solution, maintaining a constant ionic strength, I = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (NaNO₃) at 25 ± 1 °C (thermostated). pH-volume (of standard 0.1 mol dm⁻³ NaOH) data, prior to appearance of any turbidity, as the averages of three titrations, were accepted for calculating the equilibrium constants using SCOGS program¹¹.

Calculations of the formation constants :

The overall formation constant (β_{pqrs}) of a homometallic ternary Cu^{II}-HGG[±]-HGu complex of general formula, Cu_p(GG)_q(Gu)_r(OH)_s (Table 1), could be defined (omitting the charges) according to,

$$\beta_{pqrs} = \frac{[\text{Cu}_p(\text{GG})_q(\text{Gu})_r(\text{OH})_s]}{[\text{Cu}]^p[\text{GG}]^q[\text{Gu}]^r[\text{OH}]^s}$$

where, the stoichiometric integers, p, q and r might be positive or zero. s could be a negative number for a protonated species e.g. H₂GG⁺, H₂Gu⁺, HGG[±], HGu etc., zero for neutral species e.g. like Cu(GG)⁺, Cu(Gu)⁺ etc., positive number for hydroxo species e.g. Cu(OH)⁺, Cu(Gu)(OH) and deprotonated species, e.g. Cu(GG-H), Cu(Gu-H)⁺ etc. For 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : HGG[±] and Cu^{II} : HGu and 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : HGG[±] : HGu systems, p = 1, q = 1, r = 1; the values of s and its sign would depend upon the stoichiometry of the complex. Since the pH range of metal-ligand complex formation equilibria and hydrolytic equilibria of Cu(aq)²⁺ ion were overlapping, formation of hydroxo species, like Cu(OH)⁺, Cu(GG-H)(OH)⁻, Cu(Gu)(OH) etc. were taken into account in calculating the complex formation constants. Stoichiometries of the most probable complexes and the refined values of their formation constants (Table 1) corresponding to minimum standard deviations were accepted for calculation of the speciation curves (Figs. 2, 3), which formed the basis for elucidation of the complex formation equilibria.

References .

1. H. Sigel, *Angew. Chem. Internat.*, 1975, **14**, 394.
2. H. Sigel and R. B. Martin, *Chem. Rev.*, 1982, **82**, 385.
3. (a) J. F. Blount, H. C. Freeman, R. V. Holland and G. H. W. Milburn, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1970, **245**, 5177; (b) H. Gamp, H. Sigel and A. D. Zuberbuhler, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, **21**, 1190.
4. M. C. Lim, E. Sinn and R. B. Martin, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, **15**, 807.
5. H. Sigel, R. Griesser and B. Pries, *Z. Naterforsch (B)*, 1972, **27b**, 353.
6. T. R. Barman and G. N. Mukherjee, *J. Chem. Sci.*, 2008, **120**, 377.
7. E. J. Billo, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Lett.*, 1974, **1**, 129.
8. (a) E. W. Wilson (Jr.), M. H. Kasperian and R. B. Martin, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **52**, 5365; (b) R. B. Martin, *Met. Ions. Biol. Sys.*, 1979, **9**, 1; (c) A. Gergely, I. Nagypal and E. Farkas, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 551.
9. (a) P. Ray, *Chem. Rev.*, 1961, **61**, 313; (b) N. Kundu and P. Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **29**, 811.
10. T. R. Barman and G. N. Mukherjee, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2009, **48**, 38.
11. I. G. Sayce, *Talanta*, 1968, **15**, 1397; I. G. Sayce, *Talanta*, 1970, **18**, 653; I. G. Sayce and V. S. Sharma, *Talanta*, 1972, **19**, 831.